

EARLY MORPHOMETRIC BIOMARKERS OF SUBCLINICAL RETINOPATHY IN PEDIATRIC ANEMIA

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Abstract

Anemia remains a global health problem and one of the most common systemic disorders in childhood. Recent advances in Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and Optical Coherence Tomography Angiography (OCTA) allow the non-invasive evaluation of microvascular and structural changes in the retina, even before clinical manifestations occur. This study aimed to assess early morphometric and microcirculatory changes in the retina and optic nerve in children with iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and β -thalassemia, and to identify OCT and OCTA biomarkers that may predict subclinical retinal dysfunction.

Keywords: Anemia, β -thalassemia, OCT-angiography, retinal biomarkers, children

Materials and Methods

A total of 90 children aged 7–18 years were examined: 30 healthy controls and 60 patients with anemia (30 with IDA and 30 with β -thalassemia). All participants underwent standardized ophthalmic and hematologic examinations. OCTA (Optopol REVO FC, Poland) was used to evaluate the foveal avascular zone (FAZ) parameters – area, perimeter, and circularity index (CI), and vascular density (VD) in the superficial and peripapillary plexuses. OCT measurements included retinal thickness, ganglion cell complex (GCC), and retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL). Functional assessment was performed using static perimetry (MD and PSD indices). Hematologic parameters (Hb, RBC, MCV, and ferritin levels) were analyzed to correlate systemic and ocular findings. Statistical analyses were conducted using the Mann–Whitney U test, Kruskal–Wallis test, and Pearson correlation. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Children with IDA demonstrated a significant reduction in the FAZ circularity index ($p = 0.002$) and a decrease in superficial vascular density ($p = 0.038$), indicating early ischemic microcirculatory alterations. In β -thalassemia, retinal

changes were more pronounced, including enlargement of the FAZ area ($p = 0.001$), a reduction in vascular density across all capillary plexuses ($p < 0.001$), and thinning of the GCC and RNFL layers ($p < 0.001$). A positive correlation was found between Hb level and superficial vascular density ($r = 0.41, p < 0.05$), while ferritin overload in β -thalassemia was negatively correlated with RNFL thinning ($r = -0.46, p < 0.05$).

Discussion

Our findings indicate that both ischemic and neurodegenerative mechanisms may underlie subclinical retinal changes in pediatric anemia. The reduction of vascular density and FAZ circularity in IDA likely reflects early microcirculatory hypoxia, whereas in β -thalassemia, chronic hypoxia combined with iron overload-induced oxidative stress may accelerate retinal neurodegeneration. These results are consistent with previous studies reporting microvascular impairment and retinal thinning in systemic hematologic disorders. Identifying these morphometric biomarkers allows early detection of retinal dysfunction before visual symptoms appear, enabling preventive interventions and longitudinal monitoring.

Conclusion

Children with anemia, particularly β -thalassemia, exhibit statistically significant microcirculatory and structural retinal changes even in the absence of clinical retinopathy. The FAZ circularity index, superficial vascular density, and RNFL thickness are potential OCT/OCTA biomarkers for early detection and monitoring of subclinical retinal pathology. Integration of these biomarkers into pediatric ophthalmologic screening programs could help reduce the risk of vision impairment and improve early diagnostic strategies.

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